

Ruthenium(III) Catalysis in Oxidation of Cycloheptanol by Acid Bromate. A Kinetic Study

BHARAT SINGH* and SHEILA SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

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Kinetic investigations on RuIII-catalysed oxidation of cycloheptanol by acidic solution of potassium bromate in the presence of mercuric acetate as scavenger have been made in the temperature range 30–45°. The rate shows zero order kinetics both in bromate and hydrogen ions, but order of the reaction is two and one with respect to substrate and RuIII, respectively. Insignificant influence of chloride ions mercuric acetate and ionic strength of the medium was observed while the reaction showed negative dielectric effect. A transient complex, formed between $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ and cycloheptanol ($[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ being reactive species of ruthenium(III) chloride) in 1 : 2 ratio, disproportionates in a slow and rate-determining step to give reaction product and ruthenium(III) hydride which on interaction with acid bromate in a fast step regenerates catalytic species for recycling. Activation parameters have been calculated.

POTASSIUM bromate has earlier been used in oxidation of some compounds as oxidant^{1,2}.

Scant attention has been paid to explore the catalytic role of ruthenium(III) chloride with potassium bromate as an oxidant³ and the results have not been interpreted to reveal the clear picture of mode of catalysed processes. This prompted us to undertake the present investigation which constitutes the acid bromate oxidation of cycloheptanol in the presence of ruthenium(III) chloride as catalyst and mercuric acetate as scavenger.

Experimental

Aqueous solution of cycloheptanol (E. Merck), potassium bromate (AnalaR), sodium perchlorate and mercuric acetate (E. Merck) were prepared in triple-distilled water. Perchloric acid (60%; E. Merck) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) solution was prepared in hydrochloric acid of known strength. All other reagents were of analytical grade.

The reaction flasks were blackened from outside to prevent photochemical effects. Requisite volumes of all reagents including substrate were taken in a reaction vessel and thermostated at 35° for thermal equilibrium. A measured volume of potassium bromate solution, also maintained separately at the same temperature, was rapidly poured into the reaction vessel. The kinetics was followed by iodometric estimation of unconsumed bromate at regular time intervals.

Results and Discussion

Reaction mixtures containing excess bromate over cyclic alcohol in different ratios were allowed

to equilibrate at 35° for about 24 h. The estimation of unconsumed bromate showed that one mole of bromate was consumed per mole oxidation of cycloheptanol following equation (1),

The corresponding ketone was confirmed by tlc and also through the dinitrophenyl hydrazine (DNP) derivative⁴.

The kinetic data were collected at several initial concentrations of the reactants (Table 1). Zero order constants, i.e. $-dc/dt$ were calculated from

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTANTS ON RATE

[Bromate] 10 ³ M	[Substrate] 10 ³ M	[HClO ₄] 10 ³ M	$-dc/dt$ × 10 ⁷ M cm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
0.80	1.00	1.00	8.8
1.00	1.00	1.00	8.8
1.25	1.00	1.00	8.8
1.67	1.00	1.00	8.8
2.50	1.00	1.00	8.8
3.33	1.00	1.00	8.8
1.00	0.83	1.00	1.2
1.00	0.50	1.00	2.4
1.00	0.67	1.00	4.0
1.00	1.00	1.00	8.8
1.00	1.33	1.00	16.6
1.00	0.67	0.80	4.4
1.00	0.67	1.00	4.0
1.00	0.67	1.25	4.1
1.00	0.67	2.50	4.4
1.00	0.67	5.00	4.5
1.00	0.67	10.00	4.1

the plots of unconsumed bromate vs time. It was observed that values of $-dc/dt$ were constant at all initial concentrations of bromate, showing thus zero order dependence on [Bromate]. Plots of $\log -dc/dt$ against $\log$ [substrate] gave a straight line with slope nearly 2 (2.16), confirming thus second order with respect to cycloheptanol (Fig. 1C). Variation of concentration of hydrogen ions did not influence the value of $-dc/dt$ appreciably, showing thus zero order kinetics in H^+ ions,

Fig. 1. (A) (35°) and (B) (45°); plots of $(-dc/dt)$ vs $[Ru^{III}]$; $[KBrO_3]=1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[HClO_4]=1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $[Cycloheptanol]=0.67 \times 10^{-3} M$; and (C) plots of $\log(-dc/dt)$ vs $\log [Cycloheptanol]$ at 35°; $[KBrO_3]=1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[HClO_4]=1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $[Ru^{III}]=9.60 \times 10^{-2} M$.

The kinetic results recorded at various $[Ru^{III}]$, ionic strengths of the medium along with kinetic effects of successive addition of mercuric acetate, potassium chloride and acetic acid are given in Table 2. First order dependence on $[Ru^{III}]$ is evident from close resemblance between the slope values (4.0 and $6.6 \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$ at 35 and 45° , respectively) of $-dc/dt$ vs $[Ru^{III}]$ plots (Figs. 1A and B) and average value of first order constant i.e. k_1 or $-\frac{dc}{dt}/[Ru^{III}]$ (4.16 and $6.87 \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$ at 35 and 45° , respectively). Negligible effect of variation of ionic strength of the medium, addition of mercuric acetate and chloride ions on reaction rate was obvious from the kinetic data (Table 2). Positive effect of addition of acetic acid clearly proves negative dielectric effect on reaction rate. The values of energy of activation (ΔE^*), Arrhenius factor (A), entropy of activation (ΔS^*) and free energy of activation (ΔG^*) were calculated from the rate measurements at 30 , 35 , 40 and 45° (Table 3).

Negligible effect of mercuric acetate excludes the possibility of its involvement either as a catalyst or as an oxidant because it does not help the reaction proceed without bromate. Hence the function of mercuric acetate is to act as a scavenger⁸ for any Br^- ion formed in the reaction. It helps to eliminate the parallel oxidation by Br_2 which would

TABLE 2—EFFECTS OF VARIATION OF $[Ru^{III}]$ AND IONIC STRENGTH (μ) OF THE MEDIUM AND ADDITION OF MERCURIC ACETATE, POTASSIUM CHLORIDE AND ACETIC ACID ON REACTION RATE

$[Bromate]=1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Substrate]=0.67 \times 10^{-3} M$ (unless otherwise stated), $[HClO_4]=1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Hg(OAc)_2]=1.25 \times 10^{-2} M$ (unless otherwise stated), Temp. = 35° (unless otherwise stated)

$[Ru^{III}]$ $10^6 M$	μ $\times 10^3 M$	$-dc/dt^a$ $\times 10^7 cm^{-3} s^{-1}$		
5.76	2.00	2.60		
7.68	2.00	2.90		
9.60	2.00	4.00		
11.52	2.00	4.30		
15.36	2.00	5.80		
19.20	2.00	7.50		
23.00	2.00	10.00		
9.60	2.00	2.40 ^m		
9.60	1.00	3.98		
9.60	2.00	4.00		
9.60	3.00	4.04		
9.60	5.00	4.00		
9.60	6.00	4.06		
9.60	10.00	3.98		
9.60	2.00		4.0 ^a	4.02 ^d
9.60	2.00		4.02 ^b	4.00 ^e
9.60	2.00		4.0 ^c	4.04 ^f
9.60	2.00		2.7 ^g	3.00 ^j
9.60	2.00		3.3 ^h	5.38 ^k
9.60	2.00		4.5 ⁱ	6.6 ^l

^a $[Hg(OAc)_2]=3.33$, ^b 1.67 , ^c $1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[KCl]=6.00$, ^e 2.50 , ^f $1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[Acetic\ acid]=0.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ $[Substrate]=3.5$, ^h 10 , ⁱ 20% (v/v) Temp. = 30° , ^k 40° , ^l 45° ; ^m $[Substrate]=0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$.

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR ACID BROMATE OXIDATION OF CYCLOHEPTANOL

$k_1(35^\circ)$ $\times 10^{-2} M^{-2} l^3 s^{-1}$	ΔE^* $kJ\ mol^{-1}$	$\log A$	ΔS^* $JK^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$	ΔG^* $kJ\ mol^{-1}$
4.17	67.03	19.98	18.83	61.27

have been formed as a result of interaction between bromide and bromate ions.

Ruthenium(III) chloride has been reported to give a number of possible chloro species dependent on pH of the solution. Under the experimental pH range in the present investigation, $[RuCl_2(H_2O)_4]^+$ has been proposed and confirmed⁹ as reactive species dominant in the pH range 1.00–3.00. The dissociation or association possibility of chloride ions seems to be remote due to insignificant effect of chloride ions.

In acidic solution of potassium bromate, quick formation of $HBrO_3$ has been reported⁹. Zero order dependence on both $[Bromate]$ and $[H^+]$ suggests that $HBrO_3$, formed in a fast step, is itself involved in a fast step as an oxidant. The kinetic results reported in Tables 1–3 and the above statements lead us to suggest the following reaction scheme which gives the details of various steps in the title reaction.

where S is cycloheptanol

Scheme 1

Now considering above steps and on applying steady state treatment with the reasonable approximation, the rate law may be written in terms of the rate of consumption of $[BrO_2^-]$ as equation (2),

$$-\frac{d[BrO_2^-]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [Ru^{III}]_T [S]^2}{(k_{-1} + k_2) + k_1 [S]^2} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) on rearrangement may be written as equation (3),

$$-\frac{d[BrO_2^-]}{dt} = \frac{k_2 K_1 [Ru^{III}]_T [S]^2}{1 + K_1 [S]^2 + (k_2/k_{-1})} \quad (3)$$

where, $K_1 = k_1/k_{-1}$. k_2 is small as step (II) is slow and rate-determining. Hence $1 \gg (k_2/k_{-1})$ will be valid inequality. Thus in the light of the above inequality, equation (3) may be written as equation (4),

$$-\frac{d[BrO_2^-]}{dt} = \frac{k_2 K_1 [Ru^{III}]_T [S]^2}{1 + K_1 [S]^2} \quad (4)$$

when the complex is unstable K_1 is small or $1 \gg K_1 [S]^2$, then we have

$$-\frac{d[BrO_2^-]}{dt} = k_2 K_1 [Ru^{III}]_T [S]^2 \quad (5)$$

The rate law (5) accords well to the kinetic results. It is also in agreement with zero effect of ionic strength of the media, requiring an interaction between an ion and at least a dipole (step I), which fulfils also the requirement of negative dielectric effect.

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